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UNSEEN THREATS ON OUR PLATES: PESTICIDE RESIDUES IN HERBS AND SPICES

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Valued for their distinctive aromatic and medicinal properties, herbs and spices are integral to global cuisine. The cultivation and processing of herbs and spices can expose them to various environmental threats. Pesticides are used to protect crops, however, residues of these chemicals or their by-products can remain on/in crops and thus enter the food chain. The EU Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) served as a database for an overview of pesticide contamination in herbs and spices over 2011-2023. The majority of a total of 557 notifications resulted from border control (57.1%), with the highest number of products originating from India (205), as well as from Egypt, Morocco, Israel, etc. Among 122 pesticide residues detected, the most frequently encountered were organophosphates chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos methyl with 180 records, related predominantly to cumin, mint, curry and parsley. Ethylene oxide, a class 1 carcinogen, followed with 135 notifications, related to various spice mixtures, paprika, turmeric, etc. A significant number of notifications recorded the presence of carbamate carbendazim/benomyl (51), organophosphates profenofos (50), triazophos (41) and ethion (40), neonicotinoids acetamiprid (41), imidacloprid (29) and thiamethoxam (29) and bifenthrin (37), a pyrethroid ester. Carbendazim and bifenthrin are considered possible human carcinogens. About 44.5% of notifications were linked to serious risk, resulting in border rejection of approximately half of the shipments (49.2%). A diverse spectrum of pesticides used could cause a plethora of harmful effects on human health, making them not only an analytical challenge but also a risk assessment nightmare, because of their frequent co-occurrence – around one third of the notified products was simultaneously contaminated with more than one pesticide residue, of which one third had five or more residues (mostly curry and cumin), reaching a maximum of 13. Nevertheless, a well-functioning food safety system must ensure safe food environment for all.

Keywords: food safety, pesticides, public health, RASFF